

Synthesis of Some New Cyclopropane Derivatives[†]

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Dimethyloxosulfonium methylene has been generated by treating its precursor, trimethyloxosulfonium iodide, with sodium hydride in dimethylsulfoxide and reacted with a wide range of α, β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds to afford a variety of new substituted arylcyclopropyl ketones, the structures of which were supported by IR and NMR spectral studies.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infracord instrument. The NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. All the products were separated and purified by column chromatography using neutral alumina. Purity was checked by TLC.

Preparation of Trimethyloxosulfonium Iodide (1):

It was prepared by the reaction of dimethylsulfoxide with methyl iodide using the procedure of Kuhn and Trichmann⁵.

General method for the synthesis of 1-aryl-2-aryl-cyclopropanes (4a-e):

A solution of ylide (2) was prepared, under nitrogen atmosphere, from 0.002 mole of sodium hydride, 0.44 g (0.002 mole) of trimethyloxosulfonium iodide (1) and 5.0 ml of dimethylsulfoxide. The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice bath and a solution of 0.002 mole of carbonyl compound (3a-e) in 5.0 ml of dimethylsulfoxide was added rapidly. After 15 minutes the ice bath was removed and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for four hours and then at 80° for further four

METHYLENE transfer to carbon-carbon double bond had been reported by Simmon's and Smith¹, which involves the attack of methylene iodide on unsaturated compounds in the presence of zinc-copper couple, has proved to be of much synthetic value for cyclopropanation of olefinic entities. But this method was found to be inaccessible when carbon-carbon double bond was directly attached with carbonyl groups². Afterwards Corey *et al*³ and Johnson *et al*⁴ have also reported the cyclopropanation of benzalacetophenone using dimethyloxosulfonium methylene and (dimethylamino)-phenyloxosulfonium methylene respectively. However, the former ylide seems to be much versatile because it is readily generated from its corresponding salt, trimethyloxosulfonium iodide⁵, which in turn, can easily be prepared. In the present communication, some new substituted cyclopropanes have been synthesized by the reaction of dimethyloxosulfonium ylide with α, β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds.

To the ylide (2), generated from trimethyloxosulfonium iodide (1) and sodium hydride in dimethylsulfoxide, an equimolar amount of substituted α, β -unsaturated carbonyl compound (3a-e) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred first at room temperature for four hours and then at 80° for further four hours, to afford substituted arylcyclopropylketones (4a-e) in 60-70% yields (Scheme 1). The formation of products (4a-e) occurs due to selective methylene transfer reaction to the α, β -carbon-carbon double bond rather than addition to the carbonyl group. It is interesting to observe that ylide (2), when allowed to react with sterically hindered moieties, fails to undergo cyclopropanation reaction even after prolonged heating.

The structure of the products (4a-e) was supported on the basis of spectral studies. The NMR spectra (CDCl₃) exhibited multiplet in the range of δ 1.00-2.00 due to methine protons, whereas methylenic protons centered at δ 2.40-3.40. These data are in good agreement with those reported in literature³.

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hours and was kept overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was washed with ice cold water (20 ml) and the aqueous mixture was extracted with chloroform. The extracts were washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and evaporated. The product was then chromatographed over neutral alumina using benzene as eluent, and recrystallised with suitable solvents. Thus following products were synthesized.

1-(4-Tolyl)-2-benzoylcyclopropane(4a) : yield 65%, crystallized from chloroform : *n*-hexane (1 : 4), m.p. 71°, $C_{17}H_{18}O$ Calcd. C, 84.00; H, 8.00; Found : C, 83.98; H, 8.02%; ir (KBr) 1655 cm^{-1} ($\nu C=O$); nmr($CDCl_3$): δ 1.12-2.07 (m, 2H, methine), 2.30 (s, 3H, CH_3), 2.46-3.05 (m, 2H, methylene), 6.87-8.07 (m, 9H, ArH).

1-(4-Anisyl)-2-(β -naphthoyl) cyclopropane(4b) : yield 68%, crystallized from chloroform : *n*-hexane (1 : 4), m.p. 93-94°, $C_{21}H_{18}O_2$ Calcd : C, 83.44; H, 5.96; Found: C, 83.43; H, 5.92%; nmr($CDCl_3$); δ 1.10-2.17 (m, 2H, methine), 2.50-3.18 (m, 2H, methylene), 3.75 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 6.60-8.30 (m, 11H, ArH).

1-(4-Anisyl)-2-(2-thiophenoyl) cyclopropane(4c) : prepared in 60% yield, crystallized from chloroform : *n*-hexane (1 : 3), m.p. 75-77°, $C_{16}H_{14}O_2S$ Calcd : C, 69.76; H, 5.42; Found, C, 69.80; H, 5.46% nmr($CDCl_3$) δ 1.10-2.00 (m, 2H, methine), 2.40-2.84 (m, 2H, methylene), 3.86 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 6.80-8.10 (m, 7H, ArH).

1-(3,4-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-(2-thiophenoyl) cyclopropane(4d) : obtained in 60% yield, crystallized from benzene : pet. ether (b.p. 40-60°) (1 : 3), m.p. 139°, $C_{18}H_{12}O_4S$ Calcd : C, 66.17; H, 4.41; Found : C, 66.14; H, 4.44%; nmr($CDCl_3$) : δ 1.17-2.00 (m, 2H methine), 2.48-2.82 (t, 2H methylene), 5.86 (s, 2H, O- CH_2 -O), 6.48-7.90 (m, 6H, ArH).

1-(2-Furyl)-2-(β -naphthoyl) cyclopropane(4e) : prepared in 70% yield, crystallized from chloroform : *n*-hexane(1 : 3), m.p. 71°, $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ Calcd : C, 82.44; H, 5.34; Found : C, 82.40; H, 5.32%; nmr ($CDCl_3$): δ 1.20-2.08(m, 2H methine), 2.58-3.40 (m, 2H, methylene), 6.10-8.20 (m, 10H, ArH).

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